

Insect-suppressing effect of rice stubble height, tillage practices, and straw mulch in a wetland rice-cowpea cropping pattern

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In the Philippines, wetland rice farmers with no irrigation establish cowpeas by zero tillage (broadcasting seed into recently harvested rice fields) to exploit residual soil moisture for seed germination. When traditional rice varieties are grown in the rainfed areas, the stubble after harvest is tall (30–60 cm). With the short-statured, improved varieties, the stubble is much shorter (10–30 cm). We tested the effect of rice stubble height (2, 15, 30, 45, and 60 cm) of transplanted IR36 (25- \times 25-cm spacing) on pre-flowering cowpea insect pests at IRRI under 2 tillage systems: 1) dibbling seed to stimulate zero tillage, and 2) a minimum tillage method of opening furrows between alternate rows of rice stubble with a plow. We compared the two systems and their stubble heights, with stubble less high tillage (plowed and harrowed twice) with and without rice straw mulch.

Because we were concerned only with pest infestation at the pre-flowering period of cowpea, all plots received equal post-flowering insecticide protection, but only half of each main plot received pre-flowering protection. Three pre-flowering cowpea insect pests were evident during the trial (see table). In addition to bean fly *Ophiomyia phaseoli*, the leafbud-feeding thrips *Thrips palmi* and the leafhopper *Empoasca biguttula* attacked the young plants. All three pests caused plant stunting, and reduced the number of pods per plant. The thrips invasion was unexpected thrips is a newly recorded cowpea pest in the Philippines. Thrips migrated into the IRRI farm from nearby watermelon fields in the surrounding Laguna area. Unfortunately the pre-flowering insecticide (carbofuran seed treatment) did not affect the thrips. Pest incidence was highest in the high-tillage plots without stubble or mulch. The presence of rice straw mulch dramatically suppressed the leafhopper and thrips populations. We suspect that the mulch interfered with the visual host-searching responses of the pests during the colonization. Bare ground evidently highlights the cowpea plants, but mulch is either repellent or unattractive.

The erect rice stubble reduced the number of all three pests. This camouflaging effect was more pronounced in those plots with tall stubble, particularly within the 15- to 30-cm range. Responses did not differ significantly beyond 30 cm. Differences in bean fly and thrips responses between the zero- and minimum-tillage plots were significant within the 2-cm stubble height. The minimum-tillage plow furrows reduced stubble density by opening bare soil. Pest reaction was similar to that to high tillage. But that effect was nullified at stubble heights of 15 cm or more. Rice

stubble height beyond 30 cm adversely affected cowpea yield. Plants in the 45- and 60-cm stubble became etiolated and set few pods. There were differences in yield potential between the various tillage systems as shown in the pre-flowering insecticide protected plots. The lowest yield was in the minimum-tillage plot with 2-cm stubble and the highest was in the zero-tillage plot with 15-cm stubble. There was also evidence of differential responses in plant tolerance for high insect pressure among the tillage systems. High tillage, with or without mulch, suffered greater yield losses than minimum tillage at 2-cm stubble height with and without pre-flowering insecticide protection.

We conclude that the 15-cm stubble height is optimal for both yield potential and pest-suppressing effects, and is suitable for either zero or minimum tillage. Erect rice stubble is an effective cultural control of early-season insect pests, and any new tillage practice or crop-establishment method should be designed to leave erect stubble in the fields to retain this inexpensive insect control method without sacrificing yield potential.

Effect of rice stubble management and tillage systems on preflowering insect pests of cowpea established after flooded rice.^a IRRI, 1978.

Rice stubble	Tillage	Insects ^b (no./15 plants)			Yield ^c (kg/ha)	
		Bean fly ^c larvae + pupae 13 DE	<i>Thrips</i> ^c 20 DE	<i>Empoasca</i> ^c 20 DE	Preflowering insecticide ^d	No preflowering insecticide
None	Plowed and harrowed twice	17 a	83 a	36 b	687 bc	316 e
Mulch	Plowed and harrowed twice	15 a	8 b	13 c	571 cd	354 e
2-cm high	Furrows plowed between rice rows	15 a	82 a	83 a	480 d	532 d
2-cm high	Dibbling in rows	12 b	9 b	53 ab	775 b	575 cd
15-cm high	Furrows plowed between rice rows	9 bc	6 b	13 c	815 b	621 c
15-cm high	Dibbling in rows	8 bc	15 b	9 cd	994 a	799 b
30-cm high	Furrows plowed between rice rows	6 c	1 b	6 cd	626 c	360 e
30-cm high	Dibbling in rows	5 c	1 b	2 d	964 a	525 d

^aAv of 3 replicates. IR36 transplanted at 25 x 25 cm. ^bWithout insecticide. DE = days after emergence. ^cMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^d1% wt/wt carbofuran seed treatment, 0.5 kg sprays of active ingredient (a.i.) monocrotophos/ha and 1.0 kg a.i. carbaryl/ha. All plots received a similar postflowering protection: sprays of 1.0 kg a.i. monocrotophos/ha at 35 and 45 DE.

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